

Unveiling the Silent Threat: Navigating Hepatitis B Challenges and Solutions

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Citation: Al Ubaidi BAA. *Unveiling the Silent Threat: Navigating Hepatitis B Challenges and Solutions*. *Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour*. 2023;2(17):1-16.

Received Date: 18 November, 2023; **Accepted Date:** 21 November, 2023; **Published Date:** 24 November, 2023

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ABSTRACT

Background: Hepatitis B infection is a global health concern, and understanding its impact on individuals and communities is essential. This case series presents a diverse range of patients with hepatitis B infection in various clinical and social contexts.

Methods: The case series encompasses a collection of real-primary care presentation scenarios, each highlighting different aspects of hepatitis B, from diagnosis and management to prevention and the implications of this infectious disease. Each case is examined in-depth, with questions, answers, and implications provided for a comprehensive understanding.

Results: The case series sheds light on the complexities of hepatitis B, covering topics such as transmission risk, serological testing, clinical presentations, co-infections, prevention strategies, and the interplay between personal and public health.

Conclusion: These cases underscore the importance of awareness, timely diagnosis, and effective management of hepatitis B. They also emphasize the crucial role of healthcare providers in educating and empowering patients to make informed decisions about their health and lifestyles. Understanding hepatitis B's diverse impact can contribute to better prevention and management strategies and ultimately reduce its burden on individuals and communities.

This case series serves as a valuable resource for healthcare professionals, educators, and the general public, fostering a deeper understanding of hepatitis B and its implications for both individual and public health.

Keywords: Hepatitis B; Diagnosis; Serological Testing; Transmission Risk; Stigma

INTRODUCTION

Hepatitis B infection (HBI) is a global public health concern that affects millions of people worldwide and carries substantial morbidity and mortality risks. It is caused by the hepatitis B virus (HBV) and is primarily transmitted through contact with infected blood and bodily fluids and can lead to both acute and chronic liver disease^[1].

In primary care settings, healthcare providers (HCPs) often encounter patients with HBI, making it imperative to understand the epidemiology, clinical manifestations, diagnostic approaches, and management of HBV. This case series aims to shed light on the clinical experiences of primary care physicians (PCPs) in diagnosing, managing, and monitoring patients with HBI, emphasizing the importance of early detection and comprehensive care to improve patient outcomes and curb the transmission of HBV. This series will also discuss the challenges faced by PCPs in managing HBI patients and potential strategies to enhance the quality of care and reduce the disease's impact on public health. Through the insights gained from these cases, we hope to contribute to the knowledge and awareness of HBI in primary care, ultimately promoting better health outcomes and the prevention of new infections^[2].

HBV primarily affects the liver, leading to inflammation and, in severe cases, liver cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC). With its ability to transmit through various routes, including perinatal, sexual, and through blood or other body fluids. HBV is a resilient and highly contagious disease. Despite the availability of a safe and effective vaccine, the burden of HBI remains substantial, especially in regions with a high prevalence^[3].

The prevalence of chronic hepatitis B infection (CHBI) worldwide is a major public health concern, affecting approximately 296 million individuals and resulting in 820,000 deaths annually. Most of these deaths are attributed to cirrhosis, liver failure, reactivation of HBV, and hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC). Developed countries typically have a lower prevalence of HBI due to the successful implementation of universal HBV vaccination programs, rigorous blood screening practices, and improved access to healthcare services, resulting in a majority of the population being immune to the virus. In contrast, developing countries, particularly in Africa, Asia, and parts of Latin America, often experience higher prevalence rates of HBI. This is due to factors such as limited access to vaccination, inadequate healthcare infrastructure, and increased rates of mother-to-child transmission. In the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries, significant progress has been made in healthcare infrastructure and access to services, with robust vaccination programs leading to reduced prevalence rates compared to many other developing nations. However, variations in HBI prevalence can still be observed within the GCC countries due to differences in healthcare systems and migrant populations^[4,5].

HBI serological testing in health services is indicated for various purposes. It is essential for the screening of high-risk individuals, such as healthcare workers, individuals with a history of risky behaviors, and those born in high-prevalence regions. Additionally, routine testing in preventive health check-ups, maternal screening during pregnancy, occupational health assessments for at-risk professionals, and screening for travelers and immigrants from high-prevalence regions are vital to prevent transmission and facilitate timely interventions (Table 1)^[6].

The cost of HBI includes both direct medical costs (such as diagnosis, treatment, hospitalization, and medications) and indirect costs (such as loss of productivity, disability, premature mortality, and detrimental effect on the

quality of life). The economic burden of chronic hepatitis B (CHB) can be significant, which may require long-term management. Liver-related complications, such as cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma, can significantly increase the financial burden. While the indirect costs of HBI have a profound impact on both individuals and society as a whole. CHB can lead to reduced work capacity and decreased society productivity^[7].

Preventing HBV through vaccination is a cost-effective strategy for reducing the economic burden of the disease. Vaccination programs have been shown to reduce the incidence of new infections and the associated costs^[8].

Serological tests play a crucial role in diagnosing and assessing the stage of HBV infection. These tests detect specific markers associated with HBV and the body's immune response. HBsAg is used to indicate active infection, while anti-HBs signifies immunity or successful vaccination (Table 1). IgM anti-HBc points to acute infection, and IgG anti-HBc suggests a past or ongoing infection (Table 1). HBeAg marks active viral replication and high infectivity, while Anti-HBe indicates reduced replication, often during recovery or treatment (Table 1). HBV DNA tests measure viral genetic material and are essential for determining viral load and monitoring treatment progress, particularly in CHB. Genotype testing identifies specific HBV strains, which can impact treatment strategies and prognosis. These tests are used in combination, and their interpretation should be done by HCPs with expertise in HBI management, considering clinical and medical history for accurate diagnosis and treatment planning^[9,10].

Table 1: Serological tests that constitute the diagnostic panel for HBV^[11]

Positive HBsAg	<u>Active Infection</u> Acute or Chronic
Positive Anti-HBs Antibody	<u>Immunity</u> Vaccination or Infection
Positive Anti-HBc Antibody (IgM, IgG)	<u>Infection</u> Current or Past
Positive HBe Antigen Positive HBe Antibodies	<u>Virulence</u> High or Low

CASE 1

A 25-year-old sexually active male patient presented to a primary care clinic. He reported having had unprotected sexual intercourse with a new partner and was concerned about the risk of contracting sexually transmitted infections (STIs). He requested STI testing and expresses his anxiety about the situation.

1.1: What are the common STIs investigations that should be considered for testing in this case?

The common STIs to consider for testing in this case include Chlamydia, Gonorrhea, Syphilis, HIV, and HBV and C. Herpes and HPV testing may also be ordered^[3,12].

1.2: What information should be obtained during the patient's history-taking process?

In addition to the sexual history, it's important to ask about any symptoms the patient may be experiencing, past STI diagnoses, and vaccination history (e.g., HPV or HBV). Assess his known risk factors^[3,12].

1.3: What tests should be conducted for each of the potential STIs?

The specific tests may include: (3, 12)

- Chlamydia and Gonorrhea: Nucleic acid amplification tests (NAATs) on urine or swab samples.
- Syphilis: Blood test to detect *Treponema pallidum* antibodies.
- HIV: HIV antibody/antigen test (4th generation) or rapid tests.
- HBV and HCV: Hepatitis B surface antigen (HBsAg) and hepatitis C antibody testing.

1.4: What should be discussed regarding the timeframe for testing after potential exposure?

The timing for testing varies depending on the specific STI. For example, Chlamydia and Gonorrhea testing can usually be done within 2-5 days after exposure. Syphilis testing may take a few weeks for reliable results. HIV and Hepatitis B testing can be done within a few weeks, but follow-up tests are often recommended^[3,12].

Clinical Implications of the Case Study^[3,12]:

- ✓ **Early Detection and Treatment:** Prompt testing and diagnosis allow for early detection and treatment of STIs, which can prevent the development of complications and further transmission to others.
- ✓ **Preventing Spread:** Identifying and treating STIs can help prevent their spread within sexual networks, ultimately reducing the overall burden of these infections in the community.
- ✓ **Education and Prevention:** A patient's concern about STIs provides an opportunity for HCPs to educate patients about safe sexual practices, including condom use, and the importance of regular testing for those at risk.
- ✓ **Mental Health and Support:** Addressing the patient's anxiety and concerns is essential. Discussing safe sex practices, offering counseling, and providing emotional support can help alleviate anxiety and encourage responsible sexual behavior.
- ✓ **Partner Notification:** If the patient is diagnosed with an STI, it's important to discuss partner notification and treatment to prevent reinfection and further transmission.

In conclusion, this case highlights the importance of open and non-judgmental communication with patients seeking STI testing after unprotected sex. Timely testing and appropriate follow-up are crucial in preventing the spread of STIs, protecting individual health, and promoting safer sexual practices.

CASE 2

The patient is a 35-year-old male hotel manager with no significant medical history. He presented with symptoms of jaundice, fatigue, and dark urine, which had developed over the past two weeks. Upon further evaluation, it was discovered that the patient had engaged in multiple unprotected sexual encounters with a known HBI partner. The serological testing was positive for HBsAg, HBeAg, HBV DNA >1,000,000 IU/m, liver Enzymes: ALT and AST levels elevated 5-fold above normal. Further investigations were done in secondary care; liver biopsy showed severe necroinflammation and fibrosis (Metavir score F3) while viral genotype displayed B2.

2.1: What is the diagnosis for his presentation and upon investigation?

The diagnosis for this patient is a severe and high virulence HBI, as evidenced by positive serological markers (HBsAg, HBeAg), elevated liver enzymes (ALT and AST), severe liver necroinflammation and fibrosis (Metavir score F3) on liver biopsy, and a high viral load of HBV DNA (>1,000,000 IU/mL). Additionally, the patient's

HBV was identified as genotype B2. This combination of clinical and laboratory findings establishes the diagnosis of a severe, high virulence HBI^[13,14].

2.2: What precautionary measures should be taken for this patient?

Precautionary measures include^[13,14]:

- Education on safe sex practices.
- Vaccination of close contacts.
- Isolation of sharp objects to prevent accidental exposure to blood.
- Strict infection control protocols in the healthcare setting.
- Avoidance of alcohol and hepatotoxic medications.

2.3: How should the high virulence of this hepatitis B infection be treated?

The treatment measures include^[13,14]:

- Antiviral therapy with tenofovir or entecavir to suppress viral replication.
- Monitoring liver function and viral load every 3-6 months.
- Immunization against hepatitis A to prevent coinfection.

2.4: What should be the appropriate course of action if there is blood leakage onto the bed sheet during the process of inserting an IV cannula?

In the event of blood leakage onto the bed sheet during the insertion of an IV cannula, it is crucial to follow immediate steps to ensure patient safety and maintain a sterile environment^[13,14]:

- ✚ **Stop the Procedure:** Cease the IV cannulation procedure immediately to prevent further blood leakage.
- ✚ **Assess the Situation:** Evaluate the patient's condition and the extent of the blood leakage to determine if any potential harm has occurred.
- ✚ **Maintain Strict Infection Control Practices:** Including hand hygiene and the use of personal protective equipment, to minimize the risk of such incidents. Properly handling situations like these is crucial for patient safety and HCPs well-being.
- ✚ **Apply Direct Pressure:** If the bleeding is from the site where the IV cannula was inserted, apply gentle direct pressure with a sterile gauze pad to control bleeding.
- ✚ **Secure the Site:** Once bleeding is controlled, secure the IV catheter in place by applying an adhesive dressing or transparent film dressing over the cannula insertion site.
- ✚ **Dispose of Contaminated Materials:** Safely discard any contaminated materials, such as gloves or gauze, into a biohazard waste container.

- ✚ **Inform the Healthcare Team:** Notify the healthcare team or a supervisor of the incident, ensuring they are aware of the situation and can provide further guidance or assess the patient's condition.
- ✚ **Monitor the Patient:** Continuously monitor the patient for any signs of adverse reactions or complications, such as hemodynamic instability or an allergic response.
- ✚ **Document the Incident:** Document the occurrence in the patient's medical record, and incident report including details of the incident, actions taken, and the patient's response.
- ✚ **Prevent Recurrence:** Review the incident to identify potential causes and take measures to prevent similar incidents in the future. This may involve additional training or refining procedures.

2.5: What is the timeline for transitioning to non-virulence?

The transition to non-virulence can vary but is typically achieved through antiviral therapy. In most cases, it takes several months to a few years to achieve viral suppression, normalized liver enzymes, and HBeAg seroconversion^[13,14].

2.6: What are the recommended follow-up procedures?

The follow-up should include^[13,14]

- Regular monitoring of liver function and viral load every 3-6 months.
- Assessment of liver fibrosis using non-invasive tests or liver biopsy.
- Continuous patient education on the importance of adherence to antiviral therapy.

Clinical Implications of the Case Study^[13,14]:

- ✓ **HCP Education:** High virulence HBI cases present a considerable challenge to HCPs. Therefore, it is imperative to underscore the critical importance of strictly adhering to universal infectious precautions and procedures when managing such cases.
- ✓ **Vaccination Education:** HCPs and household family members alike should be duly informed about the significance of receiving the HBV vaccine. This education should emphasize that vaccination is an indispensable measure in safeguarding against HBI, particularly in populations at high risk of exposure.
- ✓ **Early Diagnosis and Treatment:** It is of paramount importance to underscore the necessity of prompt diagnosis and timely initiation of treatment in cases of high virulence HBI. Timely intervention is vital in preventing severe complications. Additionally, the pivotal role of antiviral therapy in the management of high virulence infections should be emphasized.
- ✓ **Preventive Care:** Advocating for the comprehensive screening of all household family members and close contacts for STIs is of utmost importance. Such a strategy provides an early window for detection and intervention, thus mitigating the risk of STI transmission and safeguarding individual health.
- ✓ **Reducing Stigma:** The request for STI testing within the family context underscores the necessity of mitigating the stigma associated with discussions about sexual health. HCPs should strive to create a safe and non-judgmental environment where such dialogues can occur openly and without reservation.

- ✓ **Comprehensive Care:** HCPs should proactively address the patient's concerns and facilitate the necessary STI testing and counseling. Furthermore, they should underscore the importance of continuing the HBV and HAV vaccination regimen if the patient has not yet completed the full vaccine series, ensuring a holistic approach to healthcare delivery.

CASE 3

A young couple is seeking premarital counseling in a healthcare setting. As part of the counseling process, they request the results of their HBV tests. The male partner had a history of HBI, and the serological test was positive for both anti-HBs and anti-HBc (IgG). While he had negative tests for both HBsAg and serum HBV DNA.

3.1: Can you provide a diagnosis based on the serological test results for the male partner?

He had resolved HBV infection which is defined as a history of positive HBc antibody but undetectable serum HBV DNA and HBsAg with normal ALT (SGPT) levels. HBV is a mandatory notifiable disease in Bahrain, and the notification system does not breach patient confidentiality^[2,3].

3.2: What is the significance of HBV testing in premarital counseling?

HBI testing is important as it helps assess the risk of HBV transmission between partners. It's especially relevant if one partner has a history of HBI^[2,3].

3.3: How does resolved hepatitis B in the male partner affect the couple's risk of transmission?

If the male partner has resolved his HBI and has detectable anti-HBs antibodies, the risk of transmission to his partner is greatly reduced. The presence of anti-HBs indicates immunity to the virus^[2,3].

3.4: What counseling and recommendations should be provided to the couple?

The couple should be informed about the male partner's resolved infection and the implications for transmission. They should be counseled on safe sexual practices and the benefits of HBV vaccination, which can provide additional protection^[2,3].

Clinical Implications of the Case Study^[2,3]:

- ✓ **Transmission Risk Reduction:** Testing and counseling provide an opportunity to discuss the reduced risk of HBV transmission when one partner has resolved their infection. It allows for informed decisions on sexual practices and vaccination.
- ✓ **Vaccination Promotion:** The case highlights the importance of recommending HBV vaccination to the susceptible partner if they are not already vaccinated. This not only protects against HBI but also provides peace of mind.

- ✓ **Education and Awareness:** The case emphasizes the role of HCPs in educating couples about HBV and the implications for their relationship, promoting responsible sexual health practices.
- ✓ **Reducing Stigma:** Providing comprehensive counseling helps reduce the stigma associated with HBV and promotes open and honest communication between partners.

CASE 4

A 34-year-old previously healthy individual presents to the clinic with symptoms of jaundice, fatigue, dark urine, and abdominal discomfort. The patient reports recent unprotected sexual intercourse with a new partner and sharing needles for recreational drug use. Suspecting acute hepatitis B (AHB), the HCP conducts serological and clinical assessments.

4.1: What clinical symptoms and signs are commonly associated with AHB?

Common clinical symptoms and signs include jaundice (skin and sclera), fatigue, dark urine, abdominal pain, and loss of appetite. Some individuals may also experience nausea and vomiting^[13,14].

4.2: What serological markers should be assessed to diagnose AHB?

The key serological markers for diagnosing AHBI include^[13,14]:

Hepatitis B Surface Antigen (HBsAg) - Indicates active infection.

Hepatitis B e Antigen (HBeAg) - A marker of high viral replication.

Hepatitis B Core Antibody (IgM anti-HBc) - Suggests recent infection.

Liver function tests, including alanine aminotransferase (ALT) and aspartate aminotransferase (AST) to assess liver damage.

4.3: What risk factors for HBV transmission are evident in this case?

The patient's recent unprotected sexual intercourse and sharing needles for recreational drug use are high-risk behaviors for HBV transmission^[13,14].

4.4: What are the estimated transmission risk percentages for HBV through unprotected sex and needle-sharing among individuals engaged in drug abuse?

The transmission rates of HBI through unprotected sex and needle-sharing in drug abuse can vary depending on several factors. According to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), the risk of HBV transmission

through sexual contact can range from 5% to 37% per exposure, with higher risk in individuals with multiple sexual partners and those engaging in high-risk sexual behaviors^[3].

For needle-sharing among people who inject drugs (PWID), the risk of HBV transmission is substantial, especially in settings with a high prevalence of the virus. It is estimated that the risk of transmission through shared needles or drug paraphernalia is as high as 22% per exposure^[15].

It's important to note that these percentages are approximate estimates and can vary based on individual circumstances and local prevalence rates of hepatitis B^[15].

4.5: What is the prognosis for AHB, and what potential complications should be monitored?

AHB often has a favorable prognosis, with most individuals recovering completely. However, a small percentage may develop CHB. HCPs should monitor for potential complications such as fulminant hepatitis and liver failure^[13,14].

Clinical Implications of the Case Study^[13,14]:

- ✓ **Early Diagnosis and Treatment:** Timely diagnosis and assessment of AHB are critical for appropriate management and monitoring of the patient. This can help prevent complications and facilitate recovery.
- ✓ **Risk Behavior Education:** The case highlights the need for patient education about the risks associated with unprotected sexual intercourse and needle sharing. Promoting safer behaviors is essential to prevent HBV transmission.
- ✓ **Public Health Concern:** AHB is a public health concern, especially among individuals engaging in high-risk behaviors. This case emphasizes the importance of screening, vaccination, and harm reduction strategies.
- ✓ **Testing and Vaccination:** The case underscores the significance of HBV testing and vaccination in populations at risk. It's important to offer vaccination to sexual partners and individuals with risky behaviors to prevent future infections.

CASE 5

A 40-year-old man with a history of viral hepatitis B, transmitted from sharing a needle for previous drug abuse 20 years back, planning for marriage, asking about his condition and liability to develop hepatocellular cancer. At the same time, his investigation shows positive HBsAg, positive anti-HBc, negative IgM anti-HBc, negative Anti-HBs and normal ALT.

5.1: Can you provide a diagnosis based on the serological test results for the male condition?

The patient suffering from CHB infection is defined as the determination of HBsAg in serum for at least six months after acute infection. Therefore, age at the time of acute infection is of prime importance for the progression of CHB^[2,13,14].

5.2: What clinical symptoms and signs are commonly associated with CHB?

Common clinical symptoms and signs may include fatigue, jaundice, dark urine, abdominal discomfort, loss of appetite, and potential liver enlargement. However, some individuals with CHB may be asymptomatic^[2,13,14].

5.3: What serological markers should be assessed to diagnose chronic hepatitis B?

The serological markers for diagnosing chronic hepatitis B include^[2,13,14]:

Hepatitis B Surface Antigen (HBsAg) - Indicates chronic infection.

Hepatitis B e Antigen (HBeAg) and Hepatitis B e Antibody (Anti-HBe) - Indicators of viral replication and immune response.

Hepatitis B Core Antibody (IgG anti-HBc) - Suggests previous exposure.

5.4: What is the risk of HBV transmission to the spouse of the patient with CHB?

The risk of transmission to a spouse primarily depends on their vaccination and immunity status. Unvaccinated or non-immune individuals are at risk of infection, especially through sexual contact or sharing personal items such as toothbrushes or razors^[2,13,14].

5.5: What is the recommended approach to protect the spouse from potential transmission of HBV?

The recommended approach is for the spouse to undergo testing for HBV serology. If they are non-immune or unvaccinated, they should receive HBV vaccination, followed by post-vaccination serologic testing^[2,13,14].

5.6: What is the risk of patients with chronic hepatitis B developing liver cirrhosis or hepatocellular carcinoma?

The risk of patients with CHB developing liver cirrhosis or hepatocellular carcinoma varies depending on multiple factors, including the patient's age, gender, viral load, and coexisting conditions^[2,13,14].

- **Liver Cirrhosis Risk:** Among individuals with CHB, approximately 20-30% are at risk of developing liver cirrhosis over a 20- to 30-year period^[16].
- **Hepatocellular Carcinoma Risk:** The risk of developing hepatocellular carcinoma in patients with CHB is estimated to be about 15-20 times higher compared to those without HBI. The risk varies by geographic region and other factors^[17].

Clinical Implications of the Case Study^[2,15-17]:

- ✓ **Family Education:** The case underscores the importance of educating family members about the risk of HBV transmission in households with chronically infected individuals. Knowledge can help protect loved ones.
- ✓ **Preventive Measures:** Providing vaccination to non-immune spouses and family members can effectively prevent new HBI and promote community-wide prevention efforts.
- ✓ **Chronic Disease Management:** The case highlights the need for long-term management and monitoring of individuals with CHB to prevent complications, such as liver cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma.

- ✓ **Global Health Considerations:** The case highlights the importance of recognizing the global distribution of HBI and tailoring healthcare strategies to diverse populations, particularly in regions with a high prevalence of the virus.

CASE 6

A 29-year-old nurse presents with flu-like symptoms, including fever, fatigue, and joint pain. The patient recalls a needlestick injury from a patient with a known history of CHB. The physician suspected AHB and conducted HBV serological tests with presence of positive test IgM anti- HB-c.

6.1: What are the implications of a needlestick injury in HCPs involving a patient with CHB?

HCPs should be vaccinated against HBV to prevent infection. If exposed, post-exposure prophylaxis may be recommended^[15].

6.2: What post-exposure prophylaxis (PEP) is recommended following a needlestick injury?

PEP following a needlestick injury is a critical measure to prevent the transmission of bloodborne pathogens such as HBV and HIV. It typically involves the administration of appropriate antiviral medications to reduce the risk of infection. HBV Immune Globulin (HBIG): 0.06 mL/kg (or 0.5 mL) administered intramuscularly as soon as possible after exposure, ideally within 24 hours. Also administer the first dose of the HBV vaccine simultaneously with HBIG. Subsequent doses are typically given at 1 month and 6 months after the initial dose in unvaccinated HCPs^[15].

It's crucial for HCPs to assess the individual's vaccination history and tailor the PEP regimen accordingly, as recommendations may differ based on prior vaccination status^[15].

6.3: What is the risk of HBV transmission through a needlestick injury when the source patient is suffering from either acute or chronic hepatitis B, and are there specific percentage estimates for these risks?

The risk of HBV transmission through needlestick injuries can vary depending on several factors, including the patient's HBV status, the viral load, and the specifics of the exposure. Generally, the risk of transmission from an AHB or CHB patient through a needlestick injury is not easily quantified in terms of a specific percentage due to the variability of these factors^[15].

Transmission risks can be influenced by the presence of HBV surface antigen (HBsAg) in the patient's blood, the patient's HBeAg status (which indicates high viral replication and infectivity), the viral load, and the timeliness of PEP (post-exposure prophylaxis) administration^[15].

6.4: Which serological marker is most indicative of AHB in this case?

The presence of IgM anti-HBc suggests recent infection, making it indicative of AHB^[15].

Clinical Implications of the Case Study^[15]:

- ✓ **Occupational Safety:** The case study highlights the importance of strict adherence to occupational safety protocols, such as the use of safety devices, protective equipment, and vaccination, to minimize the risk of needlestick injuries and bloodborne infections.
- ✓ **Immediate Evaluation:** HCPs should emphasize the urgency of immediate medical evaluation after a needlestick injury, allowing for early detection and post-exposure prophylaxis if necessary.
- ✓ **Preventive Measures:** In healthcare settings, the emphasis on HBV vaccination, use of safety-engineered devices, and rigorous training can significantly reduce the risk of needlestick injuries and HBV transmission.

- ✓ **Occupational Health Education:** The case emphasizes the need for education and training of HCPs on occupational health risks and preventive measures to protect themselves and their patients.
- ✓ **Public Health Significance:** Needlestick injuries in healthcare settings are not only significant for individual HCPs but also for public health, as they can lead to the transmission of infectious diseases.

CASE 7

A 21-year-old college student presents for routine medical check-up and inquired about their HBV immunity status due to concerns about potential exposure on campus. The physician conducted serological tests for HBV. The result was positive for anti-HBs antibodies

7.1: What are the implications of having detectable anti-HBs antibodies?

The presence of anti-HBs indicates immunity to HBV, either through vaccination or prior exposure, offering protection against future infection^[18].

7.2: Is there a relationship between HBI and an increased risk of other STIs?

While HBI itself does not directly increase the risk of other STIs, individuals with risky sexual behaviors, such as multiple sexual partners or unprotected sex, may be at increased risk for contracting other STIs^[18].

7.3: What common sexual risk factors can contribute to both HBI and other STIs?

Risk factors include unprotected sexual intercourse, multiple sexual partners, and engaging in high-risk sexual behaviors, which can increase the likelihood of both HBI and other STIs^[18].

7.4: What are the potential complications of co-infection with HBI and other STIs?

Co-infection with HBI and other STIs can lead to more severe liver disease and complications, as well as a higher risk of transmission of both infections^[18].

Clinical Implications of the Case Study^[18]:

- ✓ **Promotion of Safe Sexual Practices:** The case study highlights the importance of promoting safe sexual practices and raising awareness about the risks associated with multiple sexual partners and unprotected sex. Educating individuals about the use of condoms and regular STI testing is crucial in preventing both HBI and other STIs.
- ✓ **Routine STI Testing:** The case underscores the significance of routine STI testing for individuals engaged in high-risk sexual behaviors, especially those with CHB. Early detection and treatment of other STIs can prevent complications and further transmission.
- ✓ **Liver Health Monitoring:** Individuals with CHB need regular monitoring of their liver health. The potential for co-infection with other STIs emphasizes the need for comprehensive healthcare, including routine liver function tests and viral load monitoring.
- ✓ **Prevention and Vaccination:** Encouraging HBV vaccination among individuals at risk is vital. This not only provides protection against HBV but also decreases the risk of liver damage due to other STIs and co-infections.
- ✓ **Comprehensive Care:** HCPs should offer holistic care to individuals with CHB, addressing both their HBV management and sexual health. This includes providing counseling on safe sexual practices and the importance of regular STI testing.

- ✓ **Public Health Perspective:** From a public health standpoint, the case study highlights the need for educational campaigns targeting at-risk populations to reduce the prevalence of HBV and other STIs. Combining efforts for prevention and awareness can have a significant impact on public health.

In conclusion, this case study illustrates the interplay between HBI and the risk of other STIs. It emphasizes the importance of comprehensive healthcare, including education, vaccination, and routine testing, to protect individuals and promote public health.

CASE 8

A 35-year-old individual with a history of jaundice, dark urine, and fatigue was presented to a primary care clinic. The patient was concerned about whether their hepatitis was infectious and sought guidance on safe sexual practices. The HCP conducted assessments and discussed how to differentiate infective from non-infective hepatitis and when and how to practice safe sex.

8.1: How can infective hepatitis (such as AHB) be differentiated from non-infective hepatitis (such as alcoholic hepatitis or drug-induced liver injury)?

Serological tests for specific hepatitis viruses and liver function tests can help differentiate infective from non-infective hepatitis. AHB, for example, is diagnosed by the presence of HBsAg in the blood^[19].

8.2: When is it safe to engage in sexual activity for an individual with infectious hepatitis?

Individuals with infectious hepatitis should wait until their physician confirms that they are no longer contagious. This depends on the specific hepatitis virus and their recovery^[19].

8.3: How can individuals with HBV protect their sexual partners from potential transmission?

Condom use is effective in reducing the risk of HBV transmission during sexual activity. It's important to communicate with sexual partners about the infection and preventive measures^[19].

CASE 9

A 30-year-old individual with a history of jaundice, fatigue, and dark urine presents to a primary care clinic. The patient is concerned about their HBV status and seeks guidance on how to differentiate between an infective (acute) and non-infective (chronic) form of HBI using serological testing. The HCP conducts assessments and discusses when and how to practice safe sex.

9.1: How can serological tests help differentiate between acute (infective) and chronic (non-infective) HBI?

Serological tests can distinguish between acute and chronic HBI by assessing specific markers such as HBsAg, Anti-HBs, HBeAg, and Anti-HBe. AHB typically presents with positive HBsAg and IgM anti-HBc, while CHB is characterized by persistent positive HBsAg and IgG anti-HBc^[19].

9.2: When is it safe to engage in sexual activity for an individual with AHB, and how should safe sex be practiced in this context?

Individuals with AHB are highly contagious, and sexual activity should be avoided until they are non-infectious, as determined by their HCP. Safe sex during this period involves abstinence or using condoms to reduce the risk of transmission^[19].

Clinical Implications of the Case Study^[19]:

- ✓ **Timely Diagnosis and Management:** The case study underscores the importance of timely serological testing to differentiate between AHB and CHB. Accurate diagnosis allows for appropriate clinical management and the implementation of preventive measures.
- ✓ **Prevention of Transmission:** Understanding the infectious state of HBV is crucial for preventing its transmission. For individuals with AHB, strict adherence to safe sex practices, including condom use, is essential to protect sexual partners from infection.
- ✓ **HCP's Role:** HCPs play a pivotal role in educating patients about the implications of their HBI diagnosis and guiding them on when it is safe to resume sexual activity. They should also provide comprehensive counseling on preventive measures.
- ✓ **Public Health Impact:** By preventing the spread of HBV through accurate diagnosis and safe sex practices, the case study highlights the potential positive impact on public health, reducing the overall burden of the disease.
- ✓ **Stigma Reduction:** The case study can help reduce the stigma associated with HBI by emphasizing that with proper management, individuals can safely engage in sexual activity without transmitting the virus.
- ✓ **Patient Empowerment:** Educating individuals about the different stages of HBI empowers them to take control of their health and make informed decisions about their sexual activities.

In conclusion, this case study demonstrates the importance of serological testing in differentiating infective and non-infective HBI and the subsequent implications for patient management, prevention of transmission, and public health impact.

CASE 10

A 42-year-old patient with a history of CHB was presented to a primary care clinic. The patient had been under regular monitoring for their condition but was unsure about when, or if, they should be referred for treatment. The HCP conducted an assessment and discussed the criteria for referral in HBI treatment.

10.1: What are the criteria for referral to treatment in chronic hepatitis B infection?

Referral for treatment is typically recommended in CHB when the patient meets certain criteria, such as having elevated ALT levels, significant liver fibrosis or cirrhosis, a high viral load, and evidence of active liver disease^[13,20,21].

10.2: How often should a patient with CHB be monitored to determine when treatment is necessary?

Monitoring should be conducted regularly, with intervals determined by the patient's disease stage, viral load, and other factors. This can be every 3-6 months for some individuals^[13,20,21].

Clinical Implications of the Case Study^[13,20,21]:

- ✓ **Timely Treatment:** The case study highlights the importance of identifying appropriate criteria for treatment referral in CHB. Timely treatment can help prevent liver damage and complications.
- ✓ **Regular Monitoring:** Regular monitoring is essential to assess the progression of HBI. HCPs play a crucial role in evaluating the need for treatment based on a patient's specific circumstances.
- ✓ **Patient Engagement:** Educating patients about the criteria for treatment referral empowers them to take an active role in managing their HBI. This understanding can lead to timely interventions.

- ✓ **Prevention of Complications:** By referring cases for treatment when necessary, HCPs can reduce the risk of long-term complications such as liver cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma.

FUNDING

Nil

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. [World Health Organization. Hepatitis B. 2021.](#)
2. [Bennett G, Richmond J, Thompson AJ. Producing health information in consultation with health workers and the hepatitis B-affected communities is worthwhile. Aust J Prim Health. 2021;27\(2\):116-121.](#)
3. [Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. Hepatitis B Questions and Answers for the Public. 2021.](#)
4. [Lim JK, Nguyen MH, Kim WR, Gish R, Perumalswami P, Jacobson IM. Prevalence of chronic hepatitis B virus infection in the United States. Am J Gastroenterol. 2020;115\(9\):1429-1438.](#)
5. [Alali AA, Abo-Shehada MN. Prevalence of Hepatitis B Virus infection in the Gulf Cooperation Council: a systematic review and meta-analysis. BMC Infectious Diseases. 2022;22\(1\):819.](#)
6. [Song JE. Diagnosis of hepatitis B. Ann Trans Med. 2016;4\(18\).](#)
7. [Sanai FM, Alghamdi M, Dugan E, et al. A tool to measure the economic impact of Hepatitis B elimination: A case study in Saudi Arabia. J Inf Pub Health. 2020;13\(11\):1715-1723.](#)
8. [Hutton DW, Tan D, So SK. Cost-effectiveness of universal hepatitis B vaccination in the United States: focusing on adults. Hepatol. 2007;46\(2\):405-415.](#)
9. [Lok ASF, McMahon BJ. Chronic hepatitis B: Update 2009. Hepatology. 2009;50\(3\):661-662.](#)
10. [Liaw YF, Chu CM. Hepatitis B virus infection. The Lancet. 2015;386\(10003\):592-605.](#)
11. [Towell V, Cowie B. Hepatitis B serology. Aust Fam Physician. 2012;41\(4\):212-214.](#)
12. [Workowski KA, Bolan GA. Sexually transmitted diseases treatment guidelines, MMWR. Recommendations and Reports: Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report. Recommendations and Reports, 2015;64\(3\):1-137.](#)
13. [Terrault NA, Bzowej NH, Chang KM. AASLD guidelines for treatment of chronic hepatitis B. Hepatology. 2018;67\(1\):1560-1599.](#)
14. [Lok AS, Zoulim F, Dusheiko G, Ghany MG. Hepatitis B cure: From discovery to regulatory approval. Hepatology. 2017;66\(4\):1296-1313.](#)
15. [Sachina BT, Banu A, Pai SB, Shahid S, Chidambara VN. Needle Sticks Injuries \(NSIs\) and Hepatitis B Vaccination status among Health Care Workers \(HCWs\) at Asia's Largest Trauma Care Centre in Bengaluru. Int J Adv Nurs Management. 2022;10\(4\):401-404.](#)
16. [Chen CJ, Yang HI, Su J, et al. Risk of hepatocellular carcinoma across a biological gradient of serum hepatitis B virus DNA level. JAMA. 2013;300\(2\):230-240.](#)
17. [Yang JD, Hainaut P, Gores GJ, Amadou A, Plymoth A, Roberts LR. A global view of hepatocellular carcinoma: trends, risk, prevention and management. Nature Reviews Gastroenterology & Hepatology. 2020;16\(10\):589-604.](#)

18. Lesi OA, Audu RA, Okwuraiwe AP, Adeleye OO, Ige FA, Iwuorah JC. Serological and virological markers of nigerian patients with hepatitis B infection. Niger J Clin Pract. 2019;22(4):534-538.
19. Dusheiko G, Agarwal K, Maini MK. New approaches to chronic hepatitis B. New England J Med. 2023;388(1):55-69.
20. Huang DQ, Lim SG. Hepatitis B: who to treat? A critical review of international guidelines. Liver Int. 2020;40:5-14.
21. Cornberg M, Tacke F, Karlsen TH. Clinical Practice Guidelines of the European Association for the study of the Liver-Advancing methodology but preserving practicability. J Hepatol. 2019;70(1):5-7.